

1 **The dynamic changes in olive fruit phenolic metabolism and its contribution to the**
2 **activation of quiescent *Colletotrichum* infection**

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21 ABSTRACT

22 Anthracnose, the most critical disease affecting olive fruits, is caused by *Colletotrichum*
23 species. While developing olive fruits are immune to the pathogen regardless of the
24 cultivar, the resistance level varies once the fruit ripens. The defense mechanisms
25 responsible for this difference in resistance are not well understood. To explore this, we
26 analyzed the phenolic metabolic pathways occurring in olive fruits and their
27 susceptibility to the pathogen during ripening in two resistant cultivars ('Empeltre' and
28 'Frantoio') and two susceptible cultivars ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo'). Overall, resistant
29 cultivars induced the synthesis of aldehydic and demethylated forms of phenols, which
30 highly inhibited fungal spore germination. In contrast, susceptible cultivars promoted
31 the synthesis of hydroxytyrosol 4-O-glucoside during ripening, a compound with no
32 antifungal effect. This study showed that the distinct phenolic profiles between resistant
33 and susceptible cultivars play a key role in determining olive fruit resistance to
34 *Colletotrichum* species.

35 **Keywords:** *Colletotrichum* sp.; phenols; olive fruit; antifungal; ripening; susceptibility,
36 resistance, olive cultivars, *Olea europaea*.

37 1. Introduction

38 Aerial fungal pathogens cause economically significant diseases in all olive growing
39 regions (*Olea europaea* L.). Among these pathogens, *Colletotrichum* species cause
40 anthracnose, the most critical disease affecting this crop (Moral et al., 2009; Talhinhos
41 et al., 2018). Under conducive environmental conditions, the pathogen can lead to
42 severe fruit rot, resulting in devastating losses in production (Cacciola et al., 2012).
43 Additionally, olive oils obtained from fruits affected by *Colletotrichum* exhibit high
44 acidity, reduced nutritional quality, and various organoleptic defects, rendering them
45 unsuitable for human consumption (Leoni et al., 2018). Fruit-rot incidence between 10-

46 20% typically leads to an increase in free acidity by more than 0.8%; consequently,
47 these oils cannot be classified as extra virgin olive oils (Leoni et al., 2018). This quality
48 degradation is even observed in oils from symptomless fruits of certain cultivars (eg.
49 ‘Arbequina’), indicating that the pathogen can impact oil quality during asymptomatic
50 colonization (Romero et al., 2022).

51 Olive anthracnose is endemic to the western Mediterranean Basin, but has spread to all
52 continents (Talhinhas et al., 2018). Several *Colletotrichum* species cause anthracnose
53 disease, with *C. godetiae* being dominant in Greece, Italy, Spain, and Tunisia (Moral et
54 al., 2021).

55 As olive fruit completes its development and begins to change colour, discernible
56 differences in fruit susceptibility to the pathogen among olive cultivars become evident
57 in the field (Moral et al., 2009). Olive fruit development progresses through various
58 ripening stages, transitioning from green to fully black skin and flesh colours.
59 Typically, olive fruits are categorized into three ripening stages based on skin colour:
60 green, turning, and ripe (Diarte et al., 2019). Developing and green fruits exhibit
61 immunity to *Colletotrichum* spp. regardless of the genotype (Moral et al., 2008).
62 However, from the turning stage, quiescent infections become active, leading to
63 characteristic fruit rot with a soapy appearance (Fig. 1). Consequently, resistant
64 cultivars clearly distinguish from susceptible varieties (Moral et al., 2009). This
65 differential resistance to the pathogen has enabled the classification of over 300
66 cultivars based on their fruit-rot incidence during epidemic seasons (Moral et al., 2017).
67 Moreover, the susceptibility of olive fruit to *Colletotrichum* increases in the presence
68 of wounds caused by the olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera oleae*), suggesting that the epicarp
69 plays a significant role in resistance to the fungus (Moral et al., 2008).

70 While green fruits remain immune to the pathogen, they tend to accumulate quiescent
71 *Colletotrichum* infections in the form of appressoria (Moral et al., 2009; Talhinhos et
72 al., 2018). The appressorium is an essential structure for the pathogen's attachment and
73 penetration of the fruit (Agosteo et al., 2015; Gomes et al., 2009). Furthermore,
74 significant changes occur in olive fruit during ripening, including alterations in weight,
75 flesh-to-stone ratio, colour, oil content, chemical composition, and enzymatic activities
76 (Menz & Vriesekoop, 2010). For instance, oil accumulates in the fruit, and
77 anthocyanins appear, darkening the fruit's colour. Simultaneously, the concentration of
78 most minor compounds, such as phenols, triterpenes, phytosterols, and tocopherols,
79 decreases during fruit ripening (Rallo et al., 2018).

80 Among minor compounds, phenols are noteworthy due to their physiological
81 importance for plants and consumer health (Rallo et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2023). Olive
82 phenols are secondary metabolites found in various plant tissues, including fruit and
83 leaves, with their variability observed to be relatively high among different cultivars
84 (Criado-Navarro et al., 2022; Expósito-Díaz et al., 2022; Miho et al., 2021). Primary
85 olive phenols include tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol, oleocanthal, oleacein, and the aglycone
86 forms of ligstroside and oleuropein. Among the latter, oleocanthal is gaining scientific
87 attention due to its nutraceutical activities, such as antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory
88 properties, despite comprising only 10% of the total phenols (100–300 mg/kg oil)
89 (Miho et al., 2018; Rallo et al., 2018). However, critical questions remain unanswered
90 regarding changes in the qualitative and quantitative profile of phenols contributing to
91 the molecular mechanisms associated with olive fruit resistance to *Colletotrichum*.

92 Phenolic compounds have been associated with the resistance of various fruits (e.g.,
93 avocado, mango, walnut, or strawberry) to necrotrophic and hemibiotrophic fungal
94 pathogens (Buonaurio et al., 2023; Prusky, 1996; Roy et al., 2018). In the case of olive

95 fruit, different phenolic compounds have been highlighted for their antifungal
96 properties against *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive scab (Buonaurio et al.,
97 2023). Additionally, numerous studies have revealed the antimicrobial properties of
98 olive pomace and oil phenols (Difonzo et al., 2021; Yakhlef et al., 2018; Zhao et al.,
99 2023). Furthermore, the loss of one or several host resistance mechanisms present in
100 developing olive fruit, including metabolic changes in the phenolic compounds, has
101 been associated with a greater susceptibility of the ripe fruit to *Colletotrichum* (Moral
102 et al., 2017). For instance, a positive correlation has been described between cultivar
103 resistance to the pathogen and total phenols of olive oils (but not in the fruit)(Moral et
104 al., 2015). Among the changes in the phenolic compounds of olive fruits during growth
105 and ripening, there is a transformation of precursor phenols (i.e., oleuropein and
106 ligstroside) to secondary compounds due to the action of the β -glucosidase enzyme (i.e.,
107 oleuropein aglycone and ligstroside aglycone) (Cecchi et al., 2015). Subsequently, the
108 aglycones undergo a second transformation to oleacein and oleocanthal due to a
109 methylesterase enzyme (Cecchi et al., 2015; Talhaoui et al., 2015). However, the roles
110 of the metabolic pathways involved in synthesizing individual phenols on the olive
111 drupe resistance to the pathogen are still lacking.

112 The present work aims to study the phenolic metabolism pathway during olive fruit
113 ripening and its impact on fruit resistance to *Colletotrichum*.

114 **2. Materials and Methods**

115 **2.1. Fungal strains and olive cultivars**

116 In the present study, we investigated olive cultivars with varying levels of susceptibility
117 to *Colletotrichum*. Phenolic analyses were conducted in 2022 using fruits from four
118 well-known cultivars: two resistant ('Empeltre' and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible
119 ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo'). Additionally, in 2023, we included the cvs. Barnea and

120 Picual, considered susceptible and moderately resistant, for inoculation bioassays
121 (Moral et al., 2017). All fruits were harvested from the World Olive Germplasm Bank
122 of Cordoba (WOGBC) located in the Andalusia region of southern Spain (37°93'32" N,
123 -4°71'89" W), at an elevation of 173 m above sea level. The entire bank, comprising
124 900 olive trees, was identified using Single Sequence Repeats (SSR) markers (Moral et
125 al., 2017). Sampling generally involved collecting two olives per cultivar, and
126 depending on the experiment, we collected developing (still growing) and/or ripe fruits.
127 Ripe fruits were selected at three ripening stages: green, turning, and ripe,
128 corresponding to green, yellow to reddish, and violet to black fruit colours, respectively
129 (Diarte et al., 2019). A single-spore culture of *C. godetiae* (strain Col-514), isolated
130 from symptomatic fruits in a commercial orchard in Cordoba in 2016, Andalusia region,
131 was utilized for inoculation experiments. Strain Col-514 was molecularly identified
132 based on ITS, TUB2, ACT, CHS-1, HIS3, GAPDJ, and ApMat DNA regions, and it
133 was selected because *C. godetiae* is highly dominant in Spain and Italy (Moral et al.,
134 2021).

135 **2.2. Inoculation of developing and ripe fruits**

136 Developing fruits of the susceptible cv. Barnea, harvested in August, underwent
137 inoculation using a spore suspension (10^6 spores/mL) of *C. godetiae* to assess their
138 resistance (Moral et al., 2017). Inoculation was performed on both non-wounded
139 (control) and wounded developing fruits to examine the effect of the epicarp on fruit
140 resistance to the pathogen. Each fruit received a 20 μ L drop of the spore suspension.
141 Wounding was induced by removing a small portion of the epicarp (approximately 5×5
142 mm) using a sterile scalpel. Disease symptoms were evaluated 10 days post-inoculation.
143 In a subsequent inoculation experiment, turning fruits of cvs. Barnea and Hojiblanca
144 (susceptible) and Picual and Frantoio (resistant) harvested in early November, were

145 inoculated according to the previous protocol. Disease assessment was conducted
146 weekly based on symptom severity (Moral et al., 2009). All inoculated fruits were kept
147 in humid chambers (plastic containers, 22 × 16 × 10 cm) with 100% relative humidity,
148 maintained at 23 ± 2°C under fluorescent lights with a 12-hour photoperiod and an
149 intensity of 350 μmol/m² s⁻¹ (Moral et al., 2008). Disease severity was estimated using
150 a rating scale ranging from 0 to 5, where 0 indicated no visible symptoms, 1 indicated
151 visible symptoms affecting less than 25% of the fruit surface, 2 indicated symptoms
152 affecting 25–49% of the surface, 3 indicated 50–74% coverage, 4 indicated 75–100%
153 coverage, and 5 indicated soapy fruit (Moral et al., 2017).

154 **2.3. Chemicals and reagents**

155 All solvents utilized for the phenolic extraction process and subsequent analysis were
156 of HPLC (High-Performance Liquid Chromatography) quality grade. Methanol
157 (MeOH), acetonitrile, and acetic acid were procured from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis,
158 MO, USA). Additionally, pure phenols with a purity greater than 98%, including
159 oleuropein, oleacein, oleocanthal, oleuropein aglycone, and hydroxytyrosol 4-O-
160 glucoside, were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (Steinheim, Germany) and employed
161 as standards.

162 **2.4. Sample processing for phenol analysis**

163 To prevent enzymatic processes in the fruits during extraction, they were initially
164 freeze-dried using a lyophilizer (LyoQuest model Telstar 55, Terrassa, Barcelona,
165 Spain). The fruits were first deep-frozen in liquid nitrogen, then subdivided into smaller
166 lots of 100 g, and placed in the freeze-dryer at 0.3 atm and -20 °C until reaching a
167 constant weight (5-7 days). Subsequently, the endocarp of the fruits was mechanically
168 separated, and approximately 20 g of the freeze-dried fruit pulp (mesocarp and epicarp)

169 was ground into a homogeneous powder using a small laboratory mill (Bosch
170 TSM6A013B, Germany). Following grinding, 5 g of the powder (crushed fruits) was
171 extracted twice with 25 mL of EtOH/H₂O (80:20) in the presence of 1.5 mg/mL of the
172 internal standard (syringic acid) (Cecchi et al., 2015). Subsequently, 8 mL of each
173 solution obtained was washed twice with 8 mL of hexane to remove the oil residue,
174 followed by centrifugation at 7000 rpm and filtration with a cellulose acetate membrane
175 filter of 0.45 µm pore size. The extracts were then brought to a volume of 8 mL after
176 the hexane washing and stored at -80°C until further analysis.

177 The phenolic compositions of the extracts obtained from olive fruits of the four cultivars
178 ('Empeltre', 'Frantoio', 'Hojiblanca', and 'Picudo') at the three ripening stages (green,
179 turning, and ripe stages) were analyzed using a 1200 Series liquid chromatograph
180 coupled to an Agilent 6540 QTOF tandem mass spectrometer (LC–QTOF MS/MS, Palo
181 Alto, CA, USA) equipped with an electrospray ionization unit. Before analysis, the
182 extracts were diluted 1:100 (v/v). Chromatographic separation was conducted using a
183 C18 analytical column (3.0 × 150 mm; 1.8 µm) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA,
184 USA) with the recommended preanalytical column (3.0 × 0.5 mm; 1.8 µm). The
185 analytical parameters of the LC–MS/MS method and the annotation of metabolites were
186 established according to the method developed by Expósito-Díaz et al. (2022). A
187 calibration model was prepared using the oleuropein standard, and the concentration of
188 10 individual phenols (Table 1) was estimated relative to oleuropein after normalization
189 to the internal standard.

190 **2.5. Bioassay for testing the fungicidal effect of phenolic extracts**

191 In order to evaluate the fungicidal effect of phenolic compounds, two bioassays were
192 conducted using the following active agents: a) pure individual phenolic compounds

193 (purity > 98%) acquired from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (Steinheim, Germany), and b) fruit
194 phenolic extract obtained from olive fruits. The term "fruit phenolic extract"
195 specifically refers to the phenolic fraction extracted from the fruit pulp (mesocarp and
196 epicarp).

197 In the first bioassay, seven pure individual phenolic compounds—hydroxytyrosol,
198 tyrosol, oleuropein, oleuropein aglycone, oleacein, oleocanthal, and hydroxytyrosol 4-
199 O-glucoside—were utilized. All compounds were dissolved in pure acetonitrile except
200 for hydroxytyrosol 4-O-glucoside, which was dissolved in methanol-water (80/20 v/v)
201 due to its limited solubility in acetonitrile. Subsequently, five concentrations (100,
202 1000, 4000, 7000, and 10000 mg/kg) were prepared for the fungitoxicity bioassay,
203 resulting in 35 samples (7 compounds × 5 dilutions).

204 For the second bioassay, 24 olive fruit phenolic extracts (4 cultivars × 3 fruit ripening
205 stages × 2 olive trees) were prepared as described above.

206 Both the pure individual phenolic compounds (standard solutions) and fruit phenolic
207 extracts underwent antifungal activity testing following the same analytical protocol.
208 Specifically, 200 µL of each phenolic extract was dispensed into the wells of Elisa
209 plates, which were then placed in an oven for 24 hours at 25 °C to completely evaporate
210 the extractant (ethanol, acetonitrile, and/or ultrapure water), which could be lethal to
211 the conidia.

212 Subsequently, a spore suspension of *C. godetiae* at 10⁵ spores/mL was prepared in
213 ultrapure water for the fungicide test of the dried phenolic extracts. Once the 200 µL of
214 each phenolic extract was dried (evaporated at 25 °C), 20 µL of the prepared spore
215 suspension was added to each well of Elisa plates and thoroughly mixed with the pipette

216 tip. Five analytical replicates (five inoculations in five different wells for each sample)
217 were performed to ensure the reliability of the analytical results.

218 Then, the Elisa plates containing the samples (phenol-rich spore suspension) and five
219 controls (spore suspension in sterile water) were incubated for 24 h at 24 °C in darkness.
220 After incubation, 200 µL of distilled water were added to each sample/well to dilute the
221 germinated or non-germinated spore concentration for subsequent counting under the
222 inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse 80i; Nikon Corp.).

223 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

224 The statistical analysis involved ANOVA accompanied by pairwise comparison (Tukey
225 HSD, $p \leq 0.05$) analysis to identify significant differences in the concentration of
226 identified compounds between cultivars or groups of cultivars. Before ANOVA, the
227 data were normalized by Box-Cox transformation. Then, the normality test (Shapiro-
228 Wilk) and the homogeneity of variances test (Levene's test) were performed.
229 Transformed data showed a normal distribution and homogeneous variance ($P > 0.05$).
230 Pearson correlations were also conducted in the whole set of samples (24 samples) to
231 confirm the correlation between phenolic concentration and antifungal activity.

232 For estimating the relative concentration of phenolic compounds in each analyzed
233 sample (expressed as a percentage), we employed the mass spectrometric total useful
234 signal (MSTUS) method as a normalization factor (Wu & Li, 2016). This method
235 utilizes the sum of all phenolic signals (peak areas) from the detected metabolites in a
236 sample to normalize each phenol's peak area by dividing it by the sum of all areas in
237 that sample.

238 All analyses were performed using Addinsoft XLSTAT Software (2023)
239 (<https://www.xlstat.com>).

240 **3. Results and Discussion**

241 **3.1. Antifungal activity of the phenolic compounds found in the olive fruit** 242 **mesocarp and epicarp**

243 The ability of *Colletotrichum* to colonize fruits involves spore germination, appressoria
244 formation, and breaching of the olive cuticle, leading to quiescent infection (Agosteo
245 et al., 2015). This infection remains latent during fruit development until ripening,
246 resulting in pathogen reactivation and disease development (Cacciola et al., 2012).
247 Subsequently, olive fruit susceptibility to the pathogen increases during ripening, while
248 in parallel, there is a decrease in total phenolic compounds (Moral et al., 2015). There
249 are notable differences between cultivars concerning the symptom severity caused by
250 the pathogen, which can be explained by the biochemical composition of the fruit and
251 other defence mechanisms (Moral et al., 2009; Riolo et al., 2023).

252 To confirm the high resistance of developing fruit to the pathogen, regardless of the
253 presence of the epicarp, we inoculated developing fruits of the susceptible cv. Barnea.
254 Wounded and unwounded developing fruits were immune to the pathogen, consistent
255 with field observations (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2017). The antifungal effects
256 of the pericarp and mesocarp phenolic extracts (ethanol-water, 80:20 v/v) from
257 developing fruits were then evaluated by spore germinating tests (Moral et al., 2018;
258 Prusky, 1996). Pericarp and mesocarp phenolic extracts inhibited spore germination by
259 over 90%. Spore germination with appressoria was absent in the pericarp extract,
260 whereas it was only 3% in the mesocarp extract. In comparison, 83% of spores
261 germinated in water formed this structure (Supplementary Fig. 1).

262 These results show that the phenolic extracts of developing fruits, even from susceptible
263 genotypes, presented a noticeable antifungal activity, which is maintained until the
264 change of fruit colour in autumn-winter when epidemic outbreaks occur if weather
265 conditions are conducive (Talhinhas et al., 2018). Subsequently, during fruit
266 development and ripening, significant quantitative and qualitative changes occur in the
267 phenolic profile of the olive drupes (Cecchi et al., 2015), increasing the fruit
268 susceptibility to the pathogen (Moral et al., 2017).

269 Pathogen colonization and infection rate of turning fruits were highly genotype
270 dependent ($p < 0.001$) (Supplementary Fig. 2). For example, fruits of the susceptible
271 cvs. Barnea and Hojiblanca showed extensive pathogen colonization (severity > 3 out
272 of 5) by the 20th day after inoculation. In contrast, 'Picual' fruits, classified as resistant,
273 showed no symptoms at that evaluation time. On the 44th day after inoculation, 'Picual'
274 fruits only showed a partial fruit rot (with values of 2.5 out of 5). Finally, 'Frantoio'
275 fruits, considered one of the most resistant cultivars, showed no symptoms even after
276 44 days of inoculation (Supplementary Fig. 2).

277

278 **3.2. Antifungal activity of pure phenols on spore germination of *Colletotrichum***

279 Olive fruit phenolic extracts from liquid extractions may contain other compounds,
280 such as triterpenic acids. Therefore, spore germinating bioassays were performed using
281 seven standard phenolic solutions with high purity to test their fungicidal effect. The
282 tested phenols were hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, oleuropein, oleuropein aglycone, oleacein,
283 oleocanthal, and hydroxytyrosol 4-O-glucoside, selected due to their predominance
284 concentrations in olive fruits during ripening and also in the olive pomace after cellular
285 rupture and enzyme activation (Expósito-Díaz et al., 2022; Yılmaz-Düzyaman et al.,
286 2023).

287 A significant differential antifungal activity was observed among the analysed phenolic
288 compounds, which inhibited spore germination at variable concentrations. Oleocanthal
289 exhibited the highest inhibitory activity, followed by oleacein, oleuropein aglycone,
290 hydroxytyrosol, and tyrosol, with a total germination inhibitory activity ranging from
291 100, 1000, 4000, 7000, 7000, and 10000 mg/kg, respectively. Conversely,
292 hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside had no inhibitory effect at any of the tested
293 concentrations. On the other hand, phenols with similar structures, like hydroxytyrosol
294 and tyrosol, or oleocanthal and oleacein, exhibited comparable inhibitory effects on
295 spore germination (**Supplementary Fig. 3**). These findings suggest that certain phenols
296 may be more prevalent in specific genotypes and contribute to resistance against the
297 pathogen.

298 Similar results have also been found by other authors, which suggests that the
299 antimicrobial activity of the main phenols found in the olive pomace is attributed to the
300 dialdehydic structure, which imparts a potent antimicrobial effect comparable to that of
301 the commercial biocide glutaraldehyde. In olive pomace, the dialdehydic form of
302 decarboxymethyl elenolic acid (EDA) - like compound functions are considered an
303 antimicrobial agent (Yakhlef et al., 2018). Also, other authors have stated that pomace
304 and olive oil exhibit significant antimicrobial activity against various microorganisms.
305 This antimicrobial effect has been attributed to specific phenolic compounds, including
306 the dialdehydic form of decarboxymethyl elenolic acid, and their conjugated forms with
307 tyrosol and hydroxytyrosol (i.e., oleocanthal and oleacein, respectively) (Brenes et al.,
308 2020; Zhao et al., 2023).

309 **3.3. Antifungal activity of total fruit phenolic content at different ripening**
310 **stages**

311 The antifungal activity of fruit phenolic extracts of four cultivars – two resistant
312 ('Empeltre' and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo') – was
313 evaluated using green, turning, and ripe fruits. This evaluation aimed to establish the
314 relationship between total fruit phenolic content and its resistance to *Colletotrichum*.
315 For that, we compared the mean contents of total phenols (sum of individual phenols)
316 of the resistant and susceptible cultivars at three ripening stages (**Fig. 2**).

317 Antifungal activity tests conducted on Elisa plates showed that when 20 μL of a
318 pathogen spore suspension was exposed to 200 μL of the dried phenolic extract obtained
319 from olive green fruits with a concentration of 50000 mg/kg of total phenols completely
320 inhibited spore germination in all cultivars. However, the total phenols declined in
321 resistant and susceptible fruit cultivars during fruit ripening. Still, while the total phenol
322 concentration in the susceptible cultivars declined by 73% (around 14000 mg/kg), the
323 decrease in the resistant ones was 28% (to 36000 mg/kg) during the fruit change from
324 green to turning skin. The sharp phenolic reduction of the susceptible cultivars caused
325 the complete reduction of the antifungal activity (**Fig. 2**). Interestingly, the lesser
326 phenolic decrease of the resistant cultivars did not reduce the inhibitory effect of spore
327 germination.

328 Further decrease of the total phenols of susceptible cultivars by another 33% (to around
329 9000 mg/kg) from turning to ripe fruits further reduced their antifungal effect.
330 Moreover, a further decrease of the total phenols of resistant cultivars by another 26%
331 (to 26000 mg/kg) to reach from turning to ripe fruits caused 23% spore germination.
332 These results indicated that olive fruit ripening is accompanied by a decline in phenol
333 concentration and a consequent reduction of the antifungal effect on *Colletotrichum*
334 germination.

335 The reactivation of the latent infections by *Colletotrichum* in olives seems to be
336 influenced by the differential pattern of phenol decline during fruit ripening. This
337 pattern is similar to the activation of *C. gloeosporioides* quiescence infection, a fungal
338 pathogen that infects avocado and mango fruits, which also lose their antifungal
339 capacity as they ripen (Prusky, 1996). However, in the latter fruits, the antifungal
340 activity is concentrated in the fruit's pericarp composition rather than its mesocarp
341 (Prusky, 1996). Remarkably, the pericarp of mango and avocado fruits is significantly
342 thicker than that of olive fruits.

343 Structural characteristics of the olive drupes, such as cuticle thickness and size of
344 epidermal cells, also influence fruit resistance level to the pathogen (Gomes et al.,
345 2012). In our study, we observed that the mesocarp, once the pericarp was removed,
346 contained antifungal activity that could inhibit fungal colonization during the initial
347 stages of fruit development (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). However, further research is
348 required to confirm the differential evolution of phenolic composition between the
349 epicarp and mesocarp during fruit ripening.

350 **3.4. Changes in the concentrations of individual phenols during fruit ripening** 351 **and their effect on spore germination**

352 The analysis of the phenolic composition by LC–MS/MS indicated the presence of 10
353 main individual phenols in the olive fruit extracts (**Table 1**). To determine the
354 relationship between the fruit phenols and spore germination, we conducted a specific
355 correlation analysis between spore germination and individual phenol concentration in
356 green, turning, and ripe fruits. For that, we collected fruit of two resistant ('Empeltre'
357 and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo') cultivars (**Fig. 3**;
358 **Supplementary Table 1 and Table 2 a,b,c**).

359 The most abundant olive fruit phenols at the three ripening stages were oleuropein
360 aglycone and ligstroside (means 18126 and 11231 mg/kg). In the case of the susceptible
361 cultivars, the concentration of hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside was also relatively high
362 (mean 2767 mg/kg). Conversely, the concentration of demethyloleuropein was higher
363 in the resistant cultivars than in susceptible ones (605 vs 4 mg/kg) (**Table 1**).

364 Overall, phenolic compounds tended to decrease in concentration as the fruits ripened.
365 However, resistant cultivars exhibited a notable ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in the concentrations
366 of oleacein and demethyloleuropein throughout the ripening process. Conversely,
367 susceptible cultivars displayed a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in the hydroxytyrosol-
368 4-O-glucoside compound (**Table 1 and Supplementary Fig. 3**).

369 The effects of individual phenolic concentrations from all fruit extracts (the four
370 cultivars examined at the three development stages) were evaluated on pathogen spore
371 germination (**Fig. 3 and Supplementary Tables 2 a,b, and c**). When green fruits were
372 used, a negative ($p < 0.001$ and $r = -0.745$) correlation was observed between the spore
373 germination and oleuropein aglycone content. Nonetheless, the concentrations of seven
374 phenols showed a negative ($p \leq 0.05$) correlation to spore germination in turning fruits.
375 Conversely, spore germination was significantly ($p < 0.001$ and $r = 0.901$) induced by
376 hydroxytyrosol, hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside, and oleuropein diglucoside in the latter
377 fruits. Finally, neither antifungal nor inducing activities were detected when the
378 phenolic concentration of ripe fruit was studied (**Fig. 3 and Supplementary Tables 2**
379 **a,b,c**). This evolution in the inhibitory effect of the extracts indicates that the antifungal
380 activity in olive fruits results from initial antifungal compounds and the metabolic
381 synthesis of secondary phenols, with some of them showing higher antifungal activity.
382 In addition, this is particularly patent in turning fruit; the phenological stage allows us
383 to identify resistance levels of different olive fruits to the pathogen (Moral et al., 2009).

384 In contrast, oleuropein diglucoside and hydroxytyrosol glucoside induced the spore
385 germination of the pathogen. Thus, the hydrolysis of oleuropein diglucoside (a
386 glucoside derivative) to oleuropein (a glucoside conjugate) seems critical in activating
387 the antifungal capability. The latter result agrees with findings obtained from
388 glycosylated flavonoids in mango epicarp (Sudheeran et al., 2020). The concentration
389 of hydroxytyrosol showed a positive correlation ($p \leq 0.01$) with spore germination.
390 However, this correlation may be spurious, as it coincided with decreases in
391 hydroxytyrosol conjugated secoiridoids (oleacein and oleuropein aglycone), which
392 reported a strong negative correlation and so high antifungal activity. The same trend
393 was observed for the hydroxytyrosol derivative, hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside, also
394 positively correlated with spore germination. This positive correlation agrees with the
395 result in Fig. 3, where the germination test in the presence of this compound standard
396 showed no fungistatic effect.

397 Another significant impact of ripening was observed in the concentration decline of
398 oleuropein aglycone and ligstroside (**Supplementary Fig. 3**). Ligstroside is the
399 precursor of ligstroside aglycone and oleocanthal. During fruit ripening, from green to
400 ripen, these compounds declined in concentration from 16875 to 3968 mg/kg and 22675
401 to 3562 mg/kg, respectively. Still, that reduction was much more pronounced in the
402 susceptible cultivar group (**Supplementary Table 1**). Specifically, no significant
403 differences between resistant and susceptible cultivars were observed in green fruit for
404 ligstroside, with a mean concentration of 15134 and 18616 mg/kg, respectively.
405 However, in turning ripe fruits, differences in ligstroside concentration between
406 resistant and susceptible cultivars become more noticeable, with 12456 and 5213
407 mg/kg, respectively. Furthermore, the fruit of the resistant cultivars showed higher

408 concentrations of oleuropein aglycone than those of susceptible cultivars,
409 independently of their ripening stage (**Supplementary Table 1**).

410 The mean concentration of the total phenolic compounds in resistant cultivars was
411 approximately 50% higher than in the susceptible ones, in which the reduction of
412 oleuropein aglycone level during ripening was much more pronounced. The Pearson
413 correlations (**Fig. 3 and Supplementary Table 2 a,b,c**) also showed a high negative
414 correlation ($p < 0.01$ and $r > 0.640$) for aglycones (both ligstroside and oleuropein) and
415 oleocanthal in green fruits. This last compound has numerous antimicrobial effects
416 (Pang & Chin, 2018). Moreover, hydroxytyrosol, oleacein, or oleacanthal in
417 considerable concentrations, appear to be suitable for food preservation, and their effect
418 on the natural microbiota of certain foods and their influence on the sensorial properties
419 have been reported (Thielmann et al., 2017).

420 These results are consistent with those of (Gouvinhas et al., 2019), who indicated the
421 impact of *C. acutatum* on the phenylpropanoid pathway that synthesized different
422 phenolic compounds. The enzymatic activity and phenolic compounds are differentially
423 associated with gene expression for critical enzymes of the phenylpropanoid
424 metabolism in susceptible and resistant olive cultivars. These authors observed higher
425 basal value and a stable phenolic content throughout the fruit infection process in
426 resistant cultivars than in susceptible ones.

427 **3.5. Differentiation of the phenolic metabolic pathways between resistant and** 428 **susceptible cultivars during ripening**

429 Quantitative and qualitative variations of olive phenolic compounds during fruit
430 ripening and their correlations with host susceptibility were conducted by grouping the
431 individual phenols into four main groups according to their chemical structure

432 (Expósito-Díaz et al., 2022). Specifically, the four phenolic groups included: I)
433 oleuropein and ligstroside as precursor forms; II) aglycone forms (sum of ligstroside
434 aglycone and oleuropein aglycone); III) demethylated forms (sum of
435 demethyloleuropein, oleocanthal, and oleacein); and IV) glucoside phenols (sum of
436 hydroxytyrosol 4-O-glucoside and oleuropein diglucoside). A two-factor ANOVA was
437 performed to compare the phenolic concentration between resistant and susceptible
438 cultivars during fruit ripening (**Fig. 4**). Complementary, a qualitative comparison was
439 conducted by estimation of the relative content of each phenolic group (**Fig. 5**). The
440 results indicate that in green fruits, the predominant phenolic compounds for all the
441 olive cultivars were oleuropein and ligstroside and their aglycone forms, representing
442 between 97 and 98% of the cultivars phenolic profile. Afterward, these compounds
443 remained predominant in the turning fruits of the resistant cultivars, representing more
444 than 95% of the total phenolic profile. Conversely, oleuropein and ligstroside and their
445 aglycone forms declined in turning fruits of susceptible cultivars, meaning only
446 between 62 and 79% of total phenols.

447 Incrementations of demethylated forms concentration (demethyloleuropein,
448 oleocanthal, and oleacein) were also observed in ripe fruits of the resistant cultivars
449 (representing between 12-55% of total phenols). In contrast, there was an increase in
450 the concentration of phenol glucoside forms concentration (mainly hydroxytyrosol 4-
451 O-glucoside) in ripe fruits of susceptible cultivars (**Fig. 5**). In line with this observation,
452 the hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside did not show antifungal effect in the germination test
453 (**Supplementary Fig. 3**).

454 From a biochemical point of view, these results suggest that biodegradation of the main
455 phenolic compounds may occur at a much lower rate in resistant than in susceptible
456 cultivars (**Fig. 4**). During fruit ripening of the resistant cultivars, the main phenols are

457 transformed to aglycones and demethylated compounds such as demethylated-
458 oleuropein and dialdehydic forms of the demethylated oleuropein and ligstroside
459 aglycones, known as oleacein and oleocanthal. This biotransformation process is
460 principally activated by the β -glucosidase and methylesterase enzymes (Gentile et al.,
461 2017). Then, interfering with the activity of these enzymes could be of high agronomic
462 interest. Oleacein and oleocanthal pure standards also demonstrated a strong antifungal
463 effect, which was negatively correlated with pathogen spore germination
464 (**Supplementary Fig. 3, Fig. 3**).

465 Regarding the susceptible cultivars, the demethylated compounds were observed within
466 7-20% only in green fruits when the fruit is still resistant to the fungal attack. However,
467 demethylated compounds are not promoted in turning and ripe fruit of susceptible
468 cultivars; instead, there is an activated synthesis of glucoside compounds such as
469 hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside and oleuropein diglucoside. The synthesis of these last
470 derivatives in the group of susceptible cultivars indicates that the rapid degradation of
471 the main secoiridoid compounds releases hydroxytyrosol. Then hydroxytyrosol-4-O-
472 glucoside occurs under the effects of glycosyltransferase enzymes (Chatzikonstantinou
473 et al., 2019). Likewise, the initial oleuropein concentration in green fruits declines
474 during ripening since the glycosyltransferase would transform it directly into the
475 oleuropein diglucoside. These results reinforce the idea that hydroxytyrosol-4-O-
476 glucoside and oleuropein diglucoside would not affect spore germination. The loss of
477 antifungal activity can be explained mainly by the hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside
478 compound, which does not contain the monoterpene moiety described as the primary
479 anti-pathogenic moiety (Gentile et al., 2017).

480 **4. Conclusions**

481 Olive fruit ripening involves significant metabolic chemical changes that influence the
482 composition of phenolic compounds. These changes in the quantity and quality of
483 phenolic compounds also determine the fruit's susceptibility to *Colletotrichum*, a fungal
484 pathogen causing olive anthracnose, one of the most critical olive fruit diseases. This
485 study demonstrated that phenolic concentration declined faster in fruits of susceptible
486 cultivars than in resistant ones. Consistent with field studies (Moral et al., 2008; 2009;
487 2015; 2017), our findings suggest that fruits at the turning stage are optimal for
488 distinguishing levels of resistance of olive cultivars to the pathogen and their
489 associations with the fruit phenolic profiles. Consequently, while the green fruits
490 behave as resistant, independently of their genotype, ripe ones become susceptible to
491 the pathogen. In fruit at the turning stage, cultivar resistance to the pathogen may be
492 explained by different metabolic responses in phenolic compound biosynthesis.
493 Notably, susceptible cultivars undergo a sharp and faster degradation of the highly
494 fungi-toxic secoiridoides, which are transformed into hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside
495 and other compounds during ripening. Likewise, the bioassays using pure phenolic
496 compounds revealed the fungicidal effect of secoiridoid compounds such as oleuropein,
497 oleuropein aglycone, oleocanthal, and oleacein, while hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside
498 had no antifungal effect.

499 As a whole, findings from this research indicate that the most critical compounds
500 inhibiting spore germination are oleuropein, ligstroside, and their aglycone and
501 demethylated forms. These compounds are predominant in the green fruit of all
502 cultivars and remain dominant (representing more than 90% of total phenols) during
503 ripening, mainly in the resistant cultivars. Additionally, concentrations of total phenols
504 above 35 mg/g (or 3,5 % phenols in the mesocarp) make the green fruits of all cultivars
505 behave as resistant to pathogen colonisation.

506 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

507 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
508 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Figure 1. Olive fruit rot caused by *Colletotrichum godetiae* in field

Fig. 2. Relation between total phenol concentration in olive fruits and percentage of spore germination of *Colletotrichum godetiae*. **A.** Mean total concentration of phenols in two resistant ('Empeltre' and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo') cultivars. **B.** Percentage of spore germination in the presence of phenolic fruit extract during fruit maturation (green, turning, and ripe fruits) in the presence of phenolic fruit extracts. Means with the same letter are not significantly different according to the High Significant Different Test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Fig. 3. Pearson correlation analysis ($r = -1$ to 1) between the concentration of individual phenols in extracts from olive fruit at three ripening stages (green, turning, and ripe fruits) and the inhibiting effect in *Colletotrichum godetiae* spore germination. The correlations were based on the phenolic concentrations of two resistant ('Empeltre' and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo') cultivars. The spore germination was evaluated with the total phenolic extract obtained from fruits at the three ripening stages. Significant Pearson correlations ($*p \leq 0.05$, $**p \leq 0.01$, and $***p \leq 0.001$).

Fig. 4. Concentration of main phenols (mg/kg) at the three olive fruit ripening stages (green, turning, and ripe fruits). All phenolic concentrations were calculated as a relative concentration to the oleuropein standard. The fruit phenols are grouped according to the biotransformation process: I - Oleuropein and ligstroside, II - Oleuropein and ligstroside aglycone, III- Demethyloleuropein, oleocanthal and oleacein, IV – Hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside and oleuropein glucoside. **A** - resistant to *Colletotrichum* cultivars (‘Empeltre’ and ‘Frantoio’) and **B** – susceptible cultivars (‘Hojiblanca’ and ‘Picudo’). Means with the same letter are not significantly different according to the High Significant Different Test at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESISTANT CULTIVARS

SUSCEPTIBLE CULTIVARS

Fig. 5. Relative phenolic content (%) during olive fruit ripening (green, turning, and ripe fruits) in two resistant ('Empeltre' and 'Frantoio') and two susceptible ('Hojiblanca' and 'Picudo') cultivars calculated according to MSTUS method (Wu & Li, 2016). This include: I - Oleuropein and Ligstroside, II - Oleuropein and Aglycone Ligstroside Aglycone, III – Demethyloleuropein, Oleocanthal and Oleacein, IV – Hydroxytyrosol-4-O-glucoside and oleuropein glucoside.

Table 1. Mean concentrations (mg/kg) of the 10 principal phenolic compounds analyzed (LC-MS/MS) in the olive fruit of four cultivars with different resistance levels to *Colletotrichum godetiae*. All phenolic concentrations were estimated as a relative concentration to the oleuropein standard.

*Cultivar classification according to their resistance to the pathogen (from 0 = highly resistant to 10 = highly susceptible, Moral et al., 2017). ** Ripening stages (green, turning, and ripe fruits). ***The spore germination was measured in the presence of total phenolic extract obtained from each fruit through solid-liquid extraction as defined in the material and methods. Significant differences among samples expressed in letter symbols according to the Tukey test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Cultivar	Ripening Stages**	Cultivar classification*	Spore germination (%)***	Ligstroside	Oleuropein	Demethyloleuropein	Ligstroside Aglycone	Oleuropein Aglycone	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	Hydroxytyrosol	Hydroxytyrosol Glucoside	Oleuropein Diglucoside	Total phenols
Empeltre	Green	Resistant	0.26 b	11317 de	936a	19c	895 d	28317 a	6 ef	182 c	48 def	527d	93cd	42563 b
	Turning	ant	0.00 b	7724 e	748 bc	190 c	271 e	21340 b	10 def	1143 c	76 de	767 d	99 cd	33753 cd
	Ripe	(0.9)	45.65 ab	2954 f	424 de	2239 a	61 e	5301 de	26 bc	9861 a	33 ef	870 d	116 bc	30387 d
Frantoio	Green	Resistant	0.00 b	18949b	862 ab	0,5 c	3463 a	30454 a	18 cde	1300 c	26 ef	204 d	56 e	56903 a
	Turning	ant	0.00 b	17187 bc	836 ab	50 c	1514 bc	16368 bc	6 ef	511 c	12 f	182 d	86 cde	37378 bcd
	Ripe	(0.1)	0.00 b	9253 de	696 bc	1129 b	265 e	6989 d	22 bcd	1413 c	12 f	204 d	87 cd	21755 e
Avg. Resistant			8	11231	751	605	1079	18129	15	2402	35	459	90	37123
Hojiblanca	Green	Susceptible	1.22 c	12804 cd	753 bc	5 c	1435 c	17842 bc	34 b	2779 b	201 c	808 d	73 de	39859 bc
	Turning	ptible	97.80 a	2429 f	369 e	4 c	63 e	3148 de	3 ef	292 c	322 a	2856 b	144 ab	9990 fg
	Ripe	(8.8)	49.49 ab	669 f	183 f	3 c	7 e	330 e	1 f	134 c	212 bc	5178 a	174 a	7060 g
Picudo	Green	Susceptible	0.82 b	24426 a	1004 a	3 c	1931 b	14085 c	193 a	10830 a	260 b	1489 cd	97 cd	63609 a
	Turning	ptible	100 a	7996 e	702 bc	5 c	119 e	4098 de	2 f	175 c	91 d	2661 bc	97 cd	16158 ef
	Ripe	(9.2)	48.79 ab	2994 f	593 cd	5 c	21 e	1625 e	1 f	177 c	82 de	3607 b	82 de	9399 fg
Avg. Susceptible			50	8554	601	4	597	6855	39	2398	195	2767	112	24345